

<p style="text-align: center;">Form 18 THE PATENTS ACT, 1970 (39 of 1970) & THE PATENTS RULES 2003 REQUEST FOR EXAMINATION OF APPLICATION FOR PATENT [See section 11B and rules 20(4) (ii), 24B(1)(i)]</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">(FOR OFFICE USE ONLY)</p> <p>RQ. No.: Filing Date: Amount of Fee Paid: CR No.: Signature:</p>
<p>1. APPLICANT (S)/ OTHER INTERESTED PERSON(S) (a) Name: DR. AMOL GAWANDE (b) Nationality: AN INDIAN NATIONAL (c) Address: DR. AMOL GAWANDE (DIRECTOR) OF DR. D. Y. PATIL B-SCHOOL, TATHAWADE, PUNE - 411033, MAHARASHTRA, INDIA. (d) ¹[Date of Publication of the application under section 11A 29/10/2021]</p>	
<p>2. STATEMENT IN CASE OF REQUEST FOR EXAMINATION MADE BY THE APPLICANT(S) I/We hereby request that my/our application for patent no 202121046132 filed on 10/10/2021 For the invention titled IMMEDIATE LOWEST AMOUNT FLIGHT TICKETS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM. Shall be examined under section 12 and 13 of the Act.</p>	
<p>3. ADDRESS FOR SERVICE</p> <p>M&P IP PROTECTORS 102/04 Dwarkesh Residency, Opp. Ahram Bungalows, Thaltej, Ahmedabd – 380059, Gujarat, India.</p>	
<p style="text-align: right;">Dated this 5th day of February 2022</p> <p style="text-align: right;"></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Signature:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Name of the signatory Shaikh Mohammed Harun Gulam Rasul Masodi.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">IN/PA-3474</p> <p>To, The Controller of Patents The Patent Office at Mumbai/Delhi/Kolkata/Chennai</p>	
<p>Note: *To be signed by the applicant(s) or by his authorized registered patent agents. *Strike out the column which is/ are not applicable. *For fee: See first Schedule</p>	

Fig.1: Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management, flow Chart.

सत्यमेव जयते

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FORM – 26

THE PATENT ACT 1970 (39 of 1970) & PATENT RULE 2006

FORM FOR AUTHORISATION OF A PATENT AGENT/OR ANY PERSON IN A MATTER OF PROCEEDING

(Section 127 and 132, rule 135)

I/We, **1. Dr. Amol Gawande** (Director) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, **2. Atul Kumar** (Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, **3. Dr. Sonali Saha** (Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, **4. Ms. Suman Deokota** (Assistant Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, **5. Ms. Tejaswinee Kankekar** (Assistant Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, jointly and severally, as my Agents or Attorneys to apply for and obtain from the government of India letters of Patent in respect of an Invention entitled - **Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management System**, and also to maintain the issued Patent, and authorized them to act on my behalf in connection with the above Application and I also authorized them to sign my name in such papers and writings and to such acts, deeds and things, including substitution and/or revocation, as may be necessary or expedient and lastly I request that all official communications now or hereafter relating to the same may be addressed to them at the above address in **M&P IP Protectors – 102/04, Dwarkesh Residency, Opp. Ahram Bungalows, Thaltej, Ahmedabad – 380059**, and they be recognized as my authorized agents and/or attorneys in all proceedings incidental thereto and I hereby confirm all actions already taken by them in this matter.

Date:

Signature: _____

1. DR. AMOL GAWANDE

2. ATUL KUMAR

3. DR. SONALI SAHA

4. MS. SUMAN DEOKOTA

5. MS. TEJASWINEE KANKEKAR

To,
The Controller of Patents,
The patent Office
At Mumbai.

FORM - 9
THE PATENTS ACT, 1970
(39 of 1970)

&

The Patents Rules, 2003

REQUEST FOR PUBLICATION

[See section 11A (2); rule 24A]

I/ **Dr. Amol Gawande** (Director) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra,. **Atul Kumar** (Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, **Dr. Sonali Saha** (Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, **Ms. Suman Deokota** (Assistant Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, **Ms. Tejaswinee Kankekar** (Assistant Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, an Indian national hereby request for **Early Publication** of my application for Patent No. **202121046132** dated **10/10/2021** under section 11A(2) of the Act.

Dated this 13th day of October, 2021.

Signature: _____
Shaikh Mohammad Harun (IN/PA-3474)
Agent for the Applicant

To,
The Controller of Patents,
The Patent Office at Mumbai.

FORM 2
THE PATENT ACT 1970 &
 The Patents Rules, 2003
COMPLETE SPECIFICATION
 (See section 10 and rule 13)

TITLE OF THE INVENTION:

Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management System.

Name	Nationality	Address
Dr. Amol Gawande	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Dr. Amol Gawande (Director) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.
Dr. Atul Kumar	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Dr. Atul Kumar (Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.
Dr. Sonali Saha	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Dr. Sonali Saha (Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.
Ms. Suman Deokota	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Ms. Suman Deokota (Assistant Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.
Ms. Tejaswinee Kankekar	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Ms. Tejaswinee Kankekar (Assistant Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.

REAMBLE TO THE DESCRIPTION

<p>PROVISIONAL The following specification describes the</p>	<p>COMPLETE The following specification Invention. Particularly describes the invention and the manner in which it is to be performed.</p>
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FIELD OF THE INVENTION

Our Invention is related to an Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management System.

BACKGROUND OF THE INVENTION

From the second 50% of the twentieth century, the air transport market has gone through critical changes because of the improvement of new transportation and data correspondence advancements, liberation of the business sectors and multiplication of minimal expense transporters (LCCs) following the Liberalization of air transport.

The normal component of these cycles is that they work with spatial streams and accelerate travel, while empowering more individuals to travel less expensive and conquering the limitations of reality. The geological appearance of these cycles can be found in the progressions by which the significance of distance is diminishing.

Notwithstanding, these cycles don't concern every one of the spots on Earth and not all spots and individuals are influenced similarly albeit numerous urban communities are preferred associated over previously. Lately, Hungary is turning out to be increasingly more associated with the worldwide economy and streams, principally through Budapest, which fills in as a door to the worldwide streams.

Hence, know how much the Hungarian capital is coordinated into the air transport organizations and streams. The exploration lays on the above-examined hypothetical establishments and spotlights principally on Budapest and the job of air transportation in forming the Hungarian air transportation market/space.

Over the most recent twenty years, market Liberalization, liquidation of the Malév Hungarian Airlines in 2012, 2021 and multiplication of LCCs altogether changed the aeronautics section of Budapest, adjusting the districts' availability and spatial relations esteems impressively.

Geological examinations of minimal expense air travel have so far zeroed in essentially on network structure investigations adaptability of minimal expense model to long stretch market impacts of Liberalization meaning of catchment spaces of air terminals development of the travel industry affected by LCCs and evaluating conduct and procedures of LCCs.

By the by, various investigations have managed the Malév liquidation and its eventual outcomes, basically zeroing in on the air transportation market the travel industry and shopper government assistance impacts. Interestingly, little

consideration was paid to the space-framing job of LCCs; notwithstanding having the qualities of minimal expense plans of action (for example modest ticket costs and highlight point courses), LCCs altogether affect urban areas' expense and time spaces as the expanding number of LCCs may adjust the expense availability of specific urban areas.

OBJECTIVES OF THE INVENTION

- 1) The objective of the invention is to provide a “Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management System” is the discoveries of an examination that analyzed the most reduced airfares of full-administration network transporters and minimal expense aircrafts and planned the expense distance among any country to any country communities.
- 2) The other objective of the invention is to provide a examined return air tickets for three time spans in 92 node-1 to node-2 communities for explorers who began from Budapest.
- 3) The other objective of the invention is to provide a review depended on quantitative exploration strategies utilizing computerized web information assortment and a one of a kind Geographic information system- GIS-based planning strategy to think about airfares and envision the expense distance between Node-1 to Node-2.
- 4) The other objective of the invention is to provide a discoveries showed that minimal expense airplanes defeat full-organization network carriers by offering lower-charge air tickets, while the cost distance maps and furthermore the interest for air transport is for the most part directed by the spending furthest reaches of customers.
- 5) The other target of the innovation is to give a deal more information into the determinants of significant worth adaptabilities in the flying region and furthermore it attempts to perceive both ordinary and separating factors that sway the worth adaptabilities, in view of a comparative examination among a tremendous number of exploratory assessments in this field. The other objective of the invention is to provide some meta-logical techniques the general significance of a few main thrusts (e.g., distance, kind of ticket, nature of study and so forth) is explored.

SUMMARY OF THE INVENTION

In the exploration, we join the quantitative strategies for human geology, transport topography, monetary topography and GIS. Without fitting data sets, our examination depends basically on web information assortment, which is a much of the time utilized strategy in comparable investigates.

We portray our approach and characterize what we consider to be a LCC. Over the most recent twenty years, the development and fast spread of LCCs have altered air transport. The minimal expense plan of action was presented by Southwest Airlines in the mid-1970s and 2021s.

From the 1990s onwards, because of the continuous Liberalization of flight markets, an ever increasing number of aircrafts embraced the Southwest model, and LCCs have become significant worldwide players in aeronautics. These days, LCCs represent 29% of the overall traveler traffic and deal 39% of all aircraft seats.

The minimal expense carrier idea is regularly utilized as a homogeneous classification, yet there is neither a forward-thinking rundown of these LCCs nor an all-around acknowledged meaning of what is named a LCC. Subsequently, scholarly writing characterizes LCCs in various ways. In certain orders, carriers are considered as LCC if their ticket costs don't surpass a specific level of the costs of FSNCs on similar courses.

Others base their characterization on the degree to which the carriers embraced the fundamental elements² of the minimal expense model. Over the most recent couple of years, the insolvency of the Hungarian public transporter brought about critical changes in Budapest's air transportation market and led to the development of LCCs.

In spite of the fact that LCCs were at that point present in Hungary, their offer rose from 36% to 59 percent because of the changes (Budapest Airport 2013, 2021). As per the Hungarian Central Statistical Office data³, Budapest Airport recuperated from the disappointment of Malév as the air terminal served 9,955,961 travelers in 2021, outflanking the past pinnacle of 8.9 million enrolled in 2021.

The air terminal measurements likewise show that development actually proceeds as traveler numbers surpassed 10 million out of 2015, number of accessible front seats transcended pre-2012 levels and the normal burden factor of aircrafts rose to a record level (79%), which exhibits the expanding revenue of the two sightseers and business explorers in Hungary.

Henceforward, we break down the expense distance of European urban communities from Budapest open with departures from FSNCs and LCCs, and our outcomes are shown utilizing topical guides.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DIAGRAM

Fig.1: Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management, Flow Chart.

FIG.2: Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management, Block Diagram.

FIG.3: immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management

DESCRIPTION OF THE INVENTION

Diverse monetary, section and geographic factors can be recognized which, as demonstrated by their proper speculative assurance, may impact esteem flexibility check regards. From the past fragment we may fight that esteem

adaptabilities of interest and substitution possibilities are immovably related thoughts as indicated by a financial viewpoint.

It is captivating then to see that for quite a while, the substitutional environment expects a huge occupation in regards to the habits wherein these components apply their impact on adaptability check regards. If the basic premium for air transport would be desolately related to the compensation level, the utilizations on air transport would outline a humbler piece of the optional income for buyers with a higher optional income level than for clients with less money to spend.

Anticipating reducing fringe utility benefits from pay, this would suggest that utility disaster due to a charge augmentation will be lower for buyers with a higher additional money. Consequently, purchasers with a higher additional money would be less worth tricky, proposing a negative association between pay level and the degree of the worth adaptability of premium for air transport.

In the first place, the complete expense of movement incorporates a worth of time part. Since business voyagers by and large worth time higher than relaxation explorers, airfares appear to frame a more modest piece of their complete travel costs. This would imply that an increment in airfares prompts a more modest ascent in complete travel costs for business travelers, contrasted with recreation explorers, and consequently a lower eagerness to substitute financial for efficient benefits.

It is significant, however, to point at the underlying contrast in passage levels between business class and economy class trips. In light of the way that business class passages are for the most part substantially more- costly, the airfares actually structure an enormous piece of the complete travel costs for business class travelers and the money related impediments of an expansion in admissions will be higher than those for relaxation explorers.

The readiness to substitute financial for time benefits may in this way be higher than anticipated for business class travelers. The distinction in value flexibility esteems between business class and economy class travelers thusly appears to rely upon the contrast between the proportion of the business class versus the economy class travelers' time valuation and the proportion of business class versus economy class starting passages.

In the event that you have gone at any point ever via plane, odds are you have heard any of these terms - full assistance aircraft, conventional aircraft, minimal expense transporter, financial plan carrier. These terms fundamentally depict two kinds of business carriers. Furthermore, these two kinds are - full help carriers, otherwise called conventional aircrafts, and minimal expense carriers.

What are the main differences between the two?

While the first is self-evident - the cost - there are many more. Large numbers of whom you'll need to think about, when booking your next trip. That is valid that trips with minimal expense aircrafts will in general be less expensive, in some cases essentially less expensive, yet it's not just with regards to the cost.

With regards to EU flight pay, rules are the equivalent both for full assistance and minimal expense aircrafts. On account of the EU guidelines, you are secured against flight delays, flight scratch-offs and denied loading up.

Yet, when you begin purchasing additional items and food, it begins adding up and the cost increments. Now you might even be beginning pondering, if going with a spending plan aircraft is a smart thought, and which is all well and good. Since toward the end, a similar trip with a conventional carrier might cost about something very similar. Also, it would incorporate all additional items you need to pay for when booking a trip with a financial plan carrier.

Spending plan carriers are extraordinary in the event that you travel with as little luggage as possible. In the event that you don't require processed gear or dinner ready, in the event that you would prefer not to save a particular seat. In the event that you don't need any of these things, there is no point of paying more for a trip with a customary carrier. Why pay for something you don't actually require?

The "Shop Price Seat Pay" book capacity work process basically permits an installment guarantee prior to focusing on a booking. The essential bookability work process steps are:

1. Low Fare Shop
2. Air Price
3. Add Seats and required PNR Data.
4. Takes installment from client

If installment is affirmed, end the booking. If installment doesn't go through, discharge the seats back to the carrier (play out a disregard).

An essential outline of the work process is:

The accompanying flowchart exhibits the work process for an effective booking, in light of the related exchange.

Proposal: Ensure Availability

1. The sell demand consistently follows an Availability/Shopping demand.

2. Fares shows don't check seat accessibility.
3. Flight accessibility ought to consistently be checked before sell. This can be finished through shopping or accessibility calls.
4. 'Blind sells' will consistently get temperamental outcomes and lead to pointless alarms of issues at Travel port (instances of visually impaired sells: drop rebook, end and duplicate).

Use unbiased accessibility

- a. It is desirable over utilize impartial accessibility, as opposed to coordinate access accessibility for transporters with a consistent understanding
- b. Seamless surveying messages are definitely more effective than Direct Access questions and abuse of Direct Access raises the carrier and GDS preparing cost.
- c. Direct Access inquiries by and large expense the aircraft 3 fold the amount of to measure than a consistent question from impartial accessibility.

Origin and Destination (O&D)

- 1) Any corresponding flights required ought to be mentioned as such in accessibility/shopping.
- 2) Flight accessibility might be unique if the flight interfaces with another.

Highlight Point (P2P)

Any corresponding flights that were shopped as highlight point should be reserved as highlight point. Flight accessibility might be unique if the flight doesn't interface with another.

How do these players team up on the specialized level? To address this inquiry, we need to present and momentarily clarify some key contractions identified with flight booking. Assuming you need to turn out to be better familiar with frameworks and ideas driving the three-letter short structures, simply click on the connection to the devoted article.

A traveler administration framework (PSS) is a set-up of programming modules, supporting communications between the transporter and its clients. Its key parts are a focal or carrier reservation framework (CRS), a stock control framework (ICS), and a flight control framework (DCS.)

The PSS likewise contains or coordinates with an income the board instrument that breaks down recorded information and sets estimating rules and a web based business stage (carrier site) for flight and subordinate dissemination. Some vital participants among PSSs are New Skies by Navitaire, Altea by Amadeus, and Avanti by Bravo Aero.

What is CRS?

Peruse the fundamental articles: Airline Reservation Systems and Passenger Service Systems, Central Reservation Systems for Hotels. A focal reservation framework, likewise called a carrier or PC reservation framework, fills in as capacity for flight-related data like timetables, admissions and rules for each reserving class, traveller name records (PNRs), e-tickets, and so on It's likewise engaged with overseeing booking solicitations and ticket giving. A few aircrafts run their own CRS that might come as a piece of the PSS. However, numerous transporters like to have and oversee reservations on one of the GDSs.

From a more extensive perspective, a CRS is a critical innovation of any movement association that sells its stock on the web, in particular, inns and carriers. It permits directors to control reservations across all appropriation stages.

What is PNR?

Peruse the primary article: What is PNR?

A traveller name record (PNR) or booking document is an advanced archive that contains data about a voyager or gathering of explorers and their schedule. Each PNR has a novel code called a booking reference or record finder. On account of this number, the record can be effortlessly found in the CRS information base. A voyager buying a flight gets the code through email and can utilize it to get to flight subtleties or check in on the web.

What is GDS?

Peruse the fundamental article: How to Choose a GDS?

A Global Distribution System (GDS) is a PC network working as a mediator between travel planners and various travel specialist co-ops. The three principle GDSs to think about are Amadeus, Sabar, and Travel port.

What is NDC?

Peruse the fundamental articles: New Distribution Capability in Air Travel, NDC for Airlines: Key Providers and Implementation Scenario. Most of flights are dispersed through the intervention of GDSs, which power all the previously mentioned frameworks to trade information by means of the bygone EDIFACT convention. Subsequently, aircrafts can't gather definite data about travelers, nor would they be able to give include rich substance and a wide scope of ancillaries (like in-flight dinners or abundance stuff alternatives) to their clients. Then again, they need to pay additional charges for GDS administrations.

New Distribution Capability (NDC) standard was presented by the International Air Transport Association (IATA) in the expectation of supplanting the current situation. It permits go frameworks to impart information to one another by

means of standard travel APIs and utilizing the substance amicable XML convention.

NDC empowers transporters to get to client data, customize client experience, and sell ancillaries and seats from one source, bypassing the vast majority of the outsiders. Today, many aircrafts and IT organizations have taken on NDC capacity, yet GDS is as yet the principle merchant in the business.

Aircraft booking measure steps

For certain essentials covered, we should intently see what occurs between the snapshot of reservation by means of a movement stage and stuff recover at the objective air terminal. The entire course of this explorer/carrier association can be partitioned into a few significant stages:

1. flight search,
2. flight booking,
3. ancillary booking,
4. using preferred customer credits and focuses,
5. payment preparing,
6. ticketing,
7. check-in and boarding, and
8. baggage dealing with and recover.

On the off chance that you need to save your time, watch our video where we portray every one of the means of flight booking.

WE CLAIMS

- 1) Our Invention “Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management System” is the discoveries of an examination that analyzed the most reduced airfares of full-administration network transporters and minimal expense aircrafts and planned the expense distance among any country to any country communities. The review examined return air tickets for three time spans in 92 communities for explorers who began from Budapest. The review depended on quantitative exploration strategies utilizing computerized web information assortment and a one of a kind Geographic information system- GIS-based planning strategy to think about airfares and envision the expense distance between Node-1 to Node-2. Our discoveries showed that minimal expense aircrafts outflank full-administration network transporters by offering lower-charge air tickets, while the expense distance maps. The interest for air transport is generally dictated by the spending limit of clients. This Invention intends to offer more information into the determinants of significant worth adaptabilities in the flying region. It attempts to perceive both ordinary and separating factors that sway the worth adaptabilities, in view of a comparative examination among a huge number of test assessments in this field. Through meta-sensible methods the overall meaning of a couple of central purposes (e.g., distance, sort of ticket, nature of concentrate, etc) is investigated.
- 2) According to claim1# the invention is to a “Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management System” is the discoveries of an examination that analyzed the most reduced airfares of full-administration network transporters and minimal expense aircrafts and planned the expense distance among any country to any country communities.
- 3) According to claim1,2# the invention is to a examined return air tickets for three time spans in 92 node-1 to node-2 communities for explorers who began from Budapest and Also review depended on quantitative exploration strategies utilizing computerized web information assortment and a one of a kind Geographic information system- GIS-based planning strategy to think about airfares and envision the expense distance between Node-1 to Node-2.
- 4) According to claim1,2,3# the Invention is to a intends to offer more information into the determinants of significant worth adaptabilities in the flying region. It attempts to perceive both ordinary and separating factors that sway the worth adaptabilities, in view of a comparative examination among a huge number of test assessments in this field.

- 5) According to claim1,2,3# the Invention is to a through meta-sensible method the overall meaning of a couple of central purposes (e.g., distance, sort of ticket, nature of concentrate, etc) is investigated.

ABSTRACT

Our Invention “Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management System” is the discoveries of an examination that analyzed the most reduced airfares of full-administration network transporters and minimal expense aircrafts and planned the expense distance among any country to any country communities. The review examined return air tickets for three time spans in 92 node-1 to node-2 urban communities for explorers who began from Budapest. The review depended on quantitative exploration strategies utilizing computerized web information assortment and a one of a kind Geographic information system- GIS-based planning strategy to think about airfares and envision the expense distance between Node-1 to Node-2. Our discoveries showed that minimal expense aircrafts outflank full-administration network transporters by offering lower-charge air tickets, while the expense distance maps. This Invention intends to offer more information into the determinants of significant worth adaptabilities in the flying region. It attempts to perceive both ordinary and separating factors that sway the worth adaptabilities, in view of a comparative examination among a huge number of test assessments in this field. Through meta-sensible methods the overall meaning of a couple of central purposes (e.g., distance, sort of ticket, nature of concentrate, etc) is investigated.

Fig.1: Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management, Flow Chart.

FIG.2: Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management, Block Diagram.

FIG.3: immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management

FORM 1 THE PATENTS ACT 1970(39 of 1970) & The Patents Rules, 2003 APPLICATION FOR GRANT OF PATENT (See sections 7, 54 & 135 and rule 20(1))	<u>(FOR OFFICE USE ONLY)</u> Application No: Filing Date Amount of Fees Paid: CBR NO: Signature:
1. APPLICANTS REFERENCE / IDENTIFICATION NO. (AS ALLOTTED BY OFFICE)	

2. TYPE OF APPLICATION [Please tick (✓) at the appropriate category]

Ordinary (✓)		Convention ()		PCT-NP ()	
Divisional ()	Patent of Addition ()	Divisional ()	Patent of Addition ()	Divisional ()	Patent of Addition ()

3A. APPLICANT(S):

Name	Country of Residence	Nationality	Address
Dr. Amol Gawande	INDIA	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Dr. Amol Gawande (Director) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.
Dr. Atul Kumar	INDIA	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Dr. Atul Kumar (Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.
Dr. Sonali Saha	INDIA	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Dr. Sonali Saha (Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.
Ms. Suman Deokota	INDIA	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Ms. Suman Deokota (Assistant Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.
Ms. Tejaswinee Kankekar	INDIA	AN INDIAN NATIONAL	Ms. Tejaswinee Kankekar (Assistant Professor) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.

3B. CATEGORY OF APPLICANT [Please tick (✓) at the appropriate category]

Natural Person (✓)	Other than Natural Person ()		
	Small Entity ()	Startup ()	Others ()

4. INVENTOR(S): [Please tick (✓) at the appropriate category]

Are all the inventor(s) same as the applicant(s) named above?	Yes (✓)	No ()
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If "No", furnish the details of the inventor(s) N.A

Name	Nationality	Country of Residence	Address
NA	NA	NA	NA

5. TITLE OF THE INVENTION:

Immediate Lowest Amount Flight Tickets Management System.

6. AUTHORISED REGISTERED PATENT AGENT(S)		NA
ADDITIONAL PATENT AGENTS	NA	

7. ADDRESS FOR SERVICE OF APPLICANT/ PATENT AGENT(S) IN INDIA Dr. Amol Gawande Address: Dr. Amol Gawande (Director) of Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Tathawade, Pune - 411033, Maharashtra, India.	Mobile No.: 8059794469 E-mail: dr.bksarkar2003@yahoo.in dr.bksarkar2003@gmail.com
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8. IN CASE OF APPLICATION CLAIMING PRIORITY OF APPLICATION FILED IN CONVENTION COUNTRY, PARTICULARS OF CONVENTION APPLICATION: N.A

Country	App. Number	Filing Date	Name of the Applicant	Title of the Invention	IPC (as classified in the convention country)
NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

9. IN CASE OF PCT NATIONAL PHASE APPLICATION, PARTICULARS OF INTERNATIONAL APPLICATION FILED UNDER PATENT CO-OPERATION TREATY (PCT):

International application number	International filing date as allotted by the receiving office.
NA	NA

10. IN CASE OF DIVISIONAL APPLICATION FILED UNDER SECTION 16, PARTICULARS OF ORIGINAL (FIRST) APPLICATION: N.A

Original (first) application number	Date of filing of Original (first) application
N.A.	N.A.

11. IN CASE OF PATENT OF ADDITION FILED UNDER SECTION 54, PARTICULARS OF MAIN APPLICATION OR PATENT: N.A

Main application / patent Number	Date of filing of main application
----------------------------------	------------------------------------

N.A.	N.A.
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12. DECLARATIONS:

(i) Declaration by the Inventor:

(In case the applicant is an assignee: the inventor(s) may sign herein below or the applicant may upload the assignment or enclose the assignment with this application for patent or send the assignment by post/electronic transmission duly authenticated within the prescribed period).

We, the above named inventor is the true & first inventor for this invention and declare that the applicant herein is my assignee or legal representative:

NA

(ii) Declaration by the applicant/s in the convention country:

(In case the applicant in India is different than the applicant in the convention country: the applicant in the convention country may sign herein below or applicant in India may upload the assignment from the applicant in the convention country or enclose the said assignment with this application for patent or send the assignment by post/electronic transmission duly authenticated within the prescribed period)

I/We, the applicant(s) in the convention country declare that the applicant(s) herein is/~~are my/our~~ assignee or legal representative. : **N.A.**

(iii) Declaration by the applicants:

We, the applicants hereby declare that: -

1. We are in possession of the above-mentioned invention.
2. The **Complete Specification** relating to the invention is filed with this application.
3. The invention as disclosed in the specification uses the biological material from India and the necessary permission from the competent authority shall be submitted by us before the grant of patent to us: **N.A.**
4. There is no lawful ground of objection to the grant of the patent to me/ us.
5. We are the assignees or legal representatives of true and first inventors:
6. The application or each of the applications, particulars of which are given in Para - 8 was the first application in convention country/countries in respect of our invention: **N.A.**
7. We claim the priority from the above mentioned application filed in convention country/countries and state that no application for protection in respect of the invention had been made in a convention country before that date by us or by any person from which we derive the title: **YES**
8. Our application in India is based on international application under Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) as mentioned in Para-9: **N.A.**
9. The application is divided out of our application particulars of which is given in Para-10 and prays that this application may be treated as deemed to have been filed on N.A. Under sec.16 of the Act: **N.A.**

10. The said invention is an improvement in or modification of the invention particulars of which are given in Para-11: **N.A.**

FOLLOWING ARE THE ATTACHMENTS WITH THE APPLICATION

(a) Form 2

Item	Details	Fee	Remarks
Complete specification) #	No. of pages:		
Claim(s)	No. of claims: No. of pages:		
Abstract	No. of pages:		
Drawing(s)	No. of drawings: No. of pages:		

In case of a complete specification, if the applicant desires to adopt the drawings filed with his provisional specification as the drawings or part of the drawings for the complete specification under rule 13(4), the number of such pages filed with the provisional specification are required to be mentioned here.

1. Complete specification (in conformation with the international application)/as amended before the International Preliminary Examination Authority (IPEA), as applicable (2 copies) **N.A**
2. Sequence listing in electronic form **N.A**
3. Drawings (in conformation with the international application)/as amended before the International Preliminary Examination Authority (IPEA), as applicable (2 copies) **N.A**

total fee Rs /- **in ~~Cash~~ / Banker's Cheque /Bank Draft bearing No.....**

Date.....on..... Bank.

We hereby declare that to the best of my knowledge, information and belief the facts and matters stated herein are correct and I request that a patent may be granted to me for the said invention.

Dated :08/10/2021

To,
The Controller of Patent,
The Patent Office, at